

Secretions Magnifiques

To those who leaked, who still leak, who were told to hold it in: I wrote this for you.

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P^{reface}

Dear reader,

Human bodies are floating in a sea of salt water, alkaline water, gender water, violence water, blood water, waste water. Skin is a soft border of our own integrity, safety, reproduction, and life itself. This soft membrane is easily permeated by architectures of discipline, needles puncture our borders, ingesting us with voluntary surrender. We become a commodity and a production house of secretions, human biological imprints: blood, tears, semen, milk, sweat. As the disciplinary needle is pushed into me, the membrane is broken—osmosis, diffusion, and viscosity.

This penetration probes the deep tissue of architectural systems surrounding me and now exists within me as a chemical molecule. This intimacy with medical architecture pushes the question beyond aesthetics or form, situating architecture as a biopolitical technology for standardizing bodies and enforcing normalcy.

Architecture is wet, and it is incentivising. It seeps through membranes, penetrates the skin, and permeates the spaces we inhabit. These later chapters invite you into the world of architectural wetness and leakage—where the clinical, the pharmacological, and the personal intersect. Here, architecture is not a static entity of bricks and mortar but a biopolitical tool that shapes and transforms the human body (*Preciado, 2018*). From childhood encounters with medical institutions and mental illness to a life entangled with pills, this is a story of how bodies and spaces interact, resist, and are reshaped. This text is a meditation on seepage, transformation, and resistance—exploring what happens when systems designed to contain and observe life begin to leak out.

As a spatial practitioner, space, interiors, and architecture inform the way in which I navigate in this work. These elements are not just backgrounds but active tools that help me explore the questions posed in this text. I try to investigate how spaces, pharmacology, and biopolitical systems permeate individual and collective bodies and spaces, not merely to critique them but to seek opportunities for subversion and reconfiguration. Through my research, I aim to expose how these systems shape, destabilize, and ultimately offer avenues for transformation. This erasure of straight lines allows new pathways to be formed—just as a selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitor blocks one neurotransmitter pathway to open another.

Michel Foucault demonstrated that biopolitical systems operate not only through external structures but by penetrating individual bodies, transforming them into sites of discipline and control. "The medical gaze plunges into the body and emerges again only at the end of a complex network of statements and reasoning." (*Foucault, 1973, p. 89*) Preciado extends this argument by framing architecture and pharmacology as tools of systemic normalization that reshape bodies at molecular levels. He introduces the idea of Pharmacopornography: Pharmacopornographic control does not function through the architectural structuring of space alone but also through the microprosthetic, chemical, and semiotic transformation of the body itself." (*Preciado, 2013, p. 41*)

I write this at a time when the proliferation of psychopharmaceutical prescriptions suggests a deepening integration of medical control into everyday life, and it seems that the issues I am tackling do not have space to ooze out. Here, I am arguing for an architecture of leaking and oozing where the dialectic of wet and dry becomes a site of negotiation, and control hardens or liquefies depending on dosage. Leaks become a form of soft resistance, undermining biopolitical hygiene and surveillance. I want to contribute to this discussion not only as an active participant in the healthcare system, a university student, and a former pill head but also by arguing that these very

archetypes and systems—those that permeate and regulate our bodies—are paradoxically essential in reclaiming agency, reformation, and resistance to institutional permeation and spatial regulations.

Using the metaphor of wetness and leaking, I trace the flow between architecture, medicine, and memory, exploring how these systems standardise, control, and destabilise life. Drawing on theorists like Michel Foucault and Paul B. Preciado and others. I move from micro architectures like pills and neurotransmitters to macro architectures of homes, clinics and streets.

This thesis is about crossing boundaries, eradicating binaries, and finding new architectural typologies in leaks. Those leaks and secretions embodies not just the penetration of control systems into the body but their eventual destabilisation.

Secretions Magnifiques

Foucault's historical analysis in *Birth on the Clinic (1963)* reveals how at the time hospitals evolved from religious infirmaries to modern institutions of surveillance and categorisation. This shift reflects a transition in power from almost alchemical rule to disciplinary control, where architecture becomes a key instrument of biopolitical control. Understanding this evolution is essential for examining how contemporary spaces continue to shape and regulate human lives.

Today, these dynamics are amplified by crises such as rising mental health issues increased suicide rates and greatly increased prescriptions for teenagers. Julie Livingston (2024) highlights how pharmaceutical waste has permeated even the ecosystems, embedding psychoactive substances into soil and aquatic life. The urgency of recognizing this not only as biochemistry phenomenon but also as a political tool—one that mediates not only individual bodies but also planetary health. In this context, control differs from the traditional Foucauldian sense. This control is more ambient, meaning that biochemical governance extends beyond prescribed medical treatment to a generalized pharmacological atmosphere. It infiltrates cities, culture, schools, offices, etc. Operating as a form of self-administered regulation—one where biochemical exposure shapes behaviour and cognition beyond individual choice. This ambient control is not limited to passive exposure; it also manifests as continuous modulation similar to Deleuze's societies of control, where power no longer disciplines within enclosed institutions but disperses fluidly, embedding itself in environments that shape behaviour, cognition, and intimate life itself. (*Deleuze, 1990*) This shift signals not just misuse of pharmaceuticals, but hints to architectures that are no longer merely perceived but deployed as a system of control, where pharmacology becomes a tool of biopolitical architecture embedded in the urban fabric.

Psycho pharmaceuticals, now a \$50 billion industry as of 2020 (*Livingstone, 2024*), are projected to grow, infiltrating our lives on a molecular level. Their roots, however, stretch across centuries—from the rudimentary remedies of ancient Egypt to the office supplies branded with names of antidepressants. Medications such as PREP and PEP, amongst others, allowed pharma to enter bedroom life. That is, by now, changed the stigma over HIV in the gay community, commodifying it into a pack of pill-sized condoms. At the same time, this opened the possibility of a second type of risk-free fluid exchange, the first being pregnancy, the second being HIV, which complications killed Foucault in 1985. Pharma once again entered an intimate zone, reconfiguring social taboos and stigma. This sensual and affectionate dimension normalises not only sexual organs and fluids but allows clinical environments to regulate bodily experience not only just through control and normalisation but also through containment and exposure.

Preciado offers a compelling perspective on this trajectory in *2013 Testo Junkie*, linking the rise of Western capitalism to the birth of the modern pharmaceutical industry. The witch hunts, he argues, marked a violent turning point: the expropriation of women's bodies, the criminalisation of folk knowledge, and the transformation of natural resources into commodities. This process privatised medicinal knowledge, consolidating control over healing practices within pharmaceutical systems, and turned self-administration into an act governed by corporate and institutional oversight (Preciado, 2013, 61).

And now Soft pills and a wet medical cabinet filled with baby pink tranquillisers is the epitome of dual space: Both the Garden of Eden and the Tower of Babel. These spaces manifest the tension between architecture and pharmacology, between biopolitics and autonomy. While this juxtaposition is clear, what is not is the grey zone, where two sides meet. This grey zone was where metal, dirt, and chaos met the clinical, bleached, and absolutely 'clean', which produced the first wet space of my childhood.

1. Memory cortex

To pierce the first wet membrane of this thesis and the architectures of discipline, I must return to past—to the first moment I encountered wetness. Considering, however, that my wet conceiving with fathers sperm and mothers egg and birth in the old soviet clinic, washed up with human secretions in the dark hospital with fluorescent lights, is just a given and not in my memory cortex.

In my home, art did not consist of pastoral scenes or family portraits but of enlarged medical images and my favourite— white blood cells, microscopic anatomy, and chemical compounds. Medical supplies sometimes populated every room. The medicine cabinet, a shrine to pharmacological intervention, overflowed with pills for every imaginable affliction. I believe through an opaque medical cabinet I first encountered wetness in architecture. I could play a pharmacist at my own home. And so I did. But the boundary between pretending to cure and succumbing to the allure of those tiny, potent architectures— those pills— was thinner than I could comprehend as a child.

I spent my time at home creating imaginary cures from the very real substances that surrounded me and injecting my bunny toy with them. The clinic had invaded my domestic space, transforming it into what Foucault would describe as a mobile architecture—no longer confined to hospitals but extending its tentacles into our most intimate environments. Benjamin Dalton, drawing from Preciado, asserts that "this couch could be a bed in a psychiatric hospital ... this couch is a tentacle of the control system," (Preciado, 2013, p135) an installation of clinical architecture within the home. Preciado takes this further, tracing how the hospital's spatial logic does not just invade furniture but is internalized in the body itself—most notably in his work through the contraceptive pill. In my childhood, I was not playing doctor; I was rehearsing a spatial order in which the body itself becomes a site of medical governance. My bedroom, with its pill bottles and repurposed medical instruments, was wet and no different from the couch Preciado described.

Our home, with its medical objects and sterile aesthetics, was a reminder of the body's inherent vulnerability to surveillance and intervention, a microcosm of the larger systems of biopolitical control. Many of the homes in Eastern Europe had the same medicine cabinets; even the generic home needed to become a sanatorium (Colomina, 2008 p.32) in a capitalist system. Healthcare has become a sort of privilege; it costs, it has a long waiting list, and it has priority rules. The houses started to collect the little extensions of medicine - as pills, ointments and prescription pills as antibiotics and psychopharmaceuticals. As there was a lurking fear of not getting it when you most needed it.

Early struggles with preschool only deepened my connection to this architectural duality. Unable to stop screaming and crying in those first years, my mother often took me to her workplace at the immunology institute—a space that epitomized disciplinary architecture. Yet, unlike the cold sterility of a traditional clinic, this institute offered something more complex. While it embodied the mechanisms of biopolitical control—scientific research, surveillance of life at its most microscopic—it also contained elements of subversion. The building itself was layered with contradictions: alongside its laboratories and sterile BOX rooms were a pool, a sauna, a sunroom, and even spaces for cows, sheep, and other animals (test subjects). These unexpected features disrupted the rigid clinical aesthetic, creating pockets of anarchic possibility within the structure of control. These elements of subversion acted as lines of flight (*Deleuze Guittari, 1987*) vectors of escape that did not oppose the institution directly but instead carved out alternative modes of existence within it, dissolving the rigid boundaries between control and resistance through small ruptures, leaks, and reterritorializations. As the system of control, the institute was populated by resistance. While the sauna in a lab might seem as irrelevant - it is an anomaly. Sweating out in the sauna exposed the leaks in the institute's authority, where control was never absolute but always negotiated. This Interior allowed moments of unregulated life, where both domestic body and institutional professional exist outside their designated functions, however briefly.

Figure 1

I found my playground there— pipettes, animals, blood and serum, centrifuges, pools and sauna, and all kinds of medical equipment. All of it secreted into me.

1.2. Transition : Medicine cabinet to pill

I had a dream of a chair in a long corridor, the chair was made from thousands pills of pink Lexotanil Tablets. As i went closer to the chair in a dream tablets started glistening I did not understood what holds them together in chair shaped silhouette. It was tightly packed, but air pockets were visible between every single pill. As if air acted as glue or concrete. The chair was not only an image of some random chair, Ive seen this chair before. With the same crooked back part and soft bottom padding a bit arched legs. I sat on it multiple times waiting for the time to leave to school.

1.2.3 (Lit.) Vaistinèlè (eng. Medicine cabinet) Word vaistinèlè is used in diminutive form presenting as small, cute and not harmful.

As I grew, I began to understand these objects and spaces—the microscope slides, the vials of blood serum and pills—not just as tools but as extensions of the institutions to which they belonged. They infiltrated domestic spaces in the same manner as a needle infiltrates the body.

Figure b

My home was not just a space of belonging but a membrane where the domestic and the institutional merged — where the body became both a site of intimacy and a subject of surveillance. This happened simply through an opaque glass in the living room furniture piece that my father built himself - the medical cabinet, holding all the pills and alcohol with family pictures. Here, I would like to introduce Emma Cheattle's writings about *Maison de Verre* in Paris; I will expand on this in a later chapter 3.1. However, it is important to draw this parallel now while I am talking about medical opaque cabinets as an architectural body of permeation and surveillance. Cheattles writes about transparency “If clear glass reveals something formerly unseen, the idea that this revelation is neutral is a myth. Glass adds an unacknowledged sheen of desirability. The presence of the viewing body – either framed inside, or reflected in the glass from outside – furthers this.” (E. Cheattle 2016, p 69). The medicine cabinet was a domestic reiteration of opaque clinical glass, rehearsing body into docile actions, subjected to desire.

I was exposed to pharmaceuticals everywhere I went: my obsessive-compulsive grandfather left pills scattered throughout the house my grandmother used to give me sugar cubes with sleeping drops since I am a kid. my home was filled with medicine; and my teenage best friend was struggling with suicidal tendencies. For a moment, my environment seemed to revolve around one task: finding a cure. Preferably in a pill form.

The molecule as benzodiazepine enters your body through the mouth, dissolving in saliva. This system is where pharmaceuticals first probe the human body. This chemical compound is designed to have a dialogue with humane wetness first. The benzodiazepines come in different vessels, as in coatings and digestive materials. Some pills are designed to melt on your tongue to reach your bloodstream skipping the stomach which takes up most time. You can feel the pill attach to the lining of your tongue and immediately starts to melt. Entering your bloodstream through the epithelium lining. When it enters your brain, It floods it with GABA. It plays a crucial role in reducing neuronal excitability and promoting relaxation, sedation, and anxiolysis.

The medicine cabinet, then, was not just a repository of potential relief but a site of pharmaco-architectural power. As Preciado asserts, "These new soft biopolitical technologies adopt the form of the body they control, become part of the organism until they are inseparable and indistinguishable from it, and ultimately become subjects. In the pharmacopornographic regime, the body no longer inhabits disciplinary spaces; it is inhabited by them. Architecture exists in us. (*Preciado, 2013, p33.*) This makes a medicine cabinet a pharmaco-architectural dispositif. Which acts as an institutional administrative mechanism. In my case, it produced the standardisation of relief and the quiet normalisation of dependency. The medicine cabinet takes of a shape of vital organ administrating relief.

The way my personal dependency intertwined with the addiction to pharmaceuticals reveals just how deeply biopolitics shaped my life. My home, like the world beyond it, was moulded by these invisible forces. The molecules of benzodiazepines didn't just alter my neurochemistry—they became part of a larger network, seeping into my school lockers, missed classes, and aesthetics. It blurred the boundaries between the individual and the systemic. To unravel the institutionalized body, we must go deeper—down to the smallest scale, where the chemical panopticon is designed to reside.

2. Leaking pills

As I sit here writing, the pills I took an hour ago are subtly at work. By increasing serotonin levels and another pink pill that opens my GABA_A receptors to relieve any sight of debilitating stress, they influence not just my mood but the way I think, act, and even move my fingers across this keyboard. Serotonin—popularly called the “happiness molecule”—drives neuroplasticity, enabling the brain to rewire itself. Yet its exact role in alleviating anxiety and depression remains up for debate, as if the pill's effects are magic we've come to accept without question.

Psychopharmacology, acts as a bridge between the inner and outer worlds, altering neurotransmitters to reshape how we perceive and behave. Pills, like architecture, can be tools of sensory modulation. This is how pharmacology leaked from perception altering to also a surveillance mechanism as a part of the biopolitical architecture. Preciado describes the pill as a "chemical panopticon," a portable surveillance mechanism that programs behaviour, regulates sexuality, and reshapes bodies without the need for external supervision. It is control disguised as self-administration, a tower replaced by the watchful eyes of the user (*Preciado, 2013, p. 205*). In this way, medical surveillance has been absorbed into a personal, domestic ritual under the guise of self-care.

Hans Hollein, writing in 1968, was already thinking about how architecture extended beyond buildings and into the realm of perception, control, and the artificial manipulation of experience.

Figure 7

Figure 6

His Environmental Control Kit proposed a non-physical, portable architecture that altered how one engaged with space—anticipating the way pharmacology would become an everyday environmental modifier. In a 2009 interview, Hollein reflected on his idea of an "architecture pill," a drug that could dissolve the boundaries of perception, making rooms appear larger, smaller, or more comfortable. Hollein saw this as part of a larger expansion: “The human creates artificial conditions. That is architecture.”

While Hollein’s work was speculative, imagining an expanded field of architecture through perception, Preciado reveals how this shift has already materialized as a biopolitical force. The architecture pill is no longer a hypothetical tool of design but a mechanism of control that regulates bodies, desires, and behaviours. Where Hollein saw pharmacology as an extension of architectural experience, Preciado demonstrates that this very extension enables a regime of self-surveillance—one in which the boundaries of architecture do not dissolve into perception alone but into systems of normalization, medicalization, and control. Pills do not merely create spaces; they determine how we inhabit them. If Hollein saw space as mutable, Preciado reminds us that this mutability is never neutral. Design features create an illusion of neutrality and purity, masking the systems of power that regulate bodies within these spaces. (*Preciado, 2018,p16*) Spaces do not simply melt and pour into the body; they are engineered to shape behaviour, regulate pleasure, and administer compliance. This transformation—from architecture as perception to architecture as control—marks the moment when pharmacology fully enters the realm of biopolitical architecture.

2.1. Transition : Pill to Euphoria

Trigger warning : blood, animal death, gore.

My first pharmaceutical euphoria happened in deep rural Lithuania with stench of machine oil. Summers were raw, sweaty and primal. When i think of that summer i remember how in the august all family man slaughtered a pig, we grew couple in our backyard, for food. I was peeking through window of our house, seeing the stab in the heart, pig scream, stream of blood, burning, and cutting her open. Later i got an in depth biology lesson with my mother looking at pigs interiors, every organ tissue, function, even the tactile feel. Maybe it was first time i experienced something so visceral so invasive and yet so normalised. This memory goes hand in hand with the pill case I found couple weeks later tucked beside a holy Mary image on a worn wooden shelf. I couldn't resist my curiosity; I knew what the pill was for. It was lorazepam, without hesitation, I swallowed it, unsure of what to expect. Within 30 minutes this pastel yellow pill melted in brain , I was running through fields of dry August hay, smiling at the clouds, feeling a lightness in my body that I hadn't known before. I felt in my bones in every fibre of my body. I was opened up with euphoria, laying there half conscious.

2.2. Euphoric Markets

I applied the patch, and the effects were equal to about two Percodans. By 9:30 am., I was getting a little concerned—the high was increasing dramatically and an unavoidable somnolence was taking hold of me. By 10:30 am., the high had lost some of its euphoria and become sinisterly heavy and stuporous. My co-workers were giving me suspicious glances as my movements became exaggerated and simple tasks like hanging up the phone became a real challenge. My desk, with its usual office accoutrements, became an obstacle course that required a dexterity I was rapidly losing. By 11:00 am., it felt like I had four Percodans coursing through my bloodstream. Euphoria became heavy. - by Will Beifuss
¹(Hogshire, 1999pg 138)

Figure 3

¹ Story by Will Beifuss "sailing fentanyl seas" used as a narrative chapter in Book By Jim Hogshire, Pills a gogo.

During the 1960s, pharmaceutical advertising flourished, selling not just pills but dreams of escape and better life. Companies targeted women—especially suburban housewives, portraying pills as solutions to the “chronic” burdens of domestic life. Jim Hogshire notes how these ads framed tranquillisers as relief for both doctor and patient, casting women as perpetual complainers needing sedation for their emotional labor. The pill wasn’t just medicine; it was a biopolitical tool to maintain societal order, offering calm for the patient and productivity for the world around her (Hogshire, 1999.pg. 24).

These glossy ads, with their promises of composure and control over emotions, concealed a deeper truth: the very conditions they aimed to alleviate, were often created by the systems they upheld. By pathologizing the natural toll of gendered labor, they turned unhappiness into disorder. The pill, once a symbol of liberation, became a reinforcement of the structures it sought to relieve, masked submission and framed it as initiative. Further deepening the capitalist demand for emotional stability.

This ambiguity extends beyond the individual to societal architectures. As Peter Breggin in pills a gogo 1999 argues, psychopharmaceutical interventions in marginalized communities often act as a form of systemic exploitation or neglect. Prescribing anti-aggression drugs to inner-city youth, for instance, serves as a pretext for ignoring deeper structural inequalities. In a parallel way anti anxiety medication for suburbia housewife can deepen the exploitation inherent in the traditional family

Figure 4

Figure 5

structure. These interventions operate on two interconnected architectures: the city and the house. From the inner workings of neurotransmitters to the open-air drug markets, pharmaceuticals reshape both physical spaces and Domestic landscapes.

What is marketed beyond the name, the shape, and the color of the pill is not just a substance but an alien state of euphoria—a force capable of rupturing normative perception. Reading Raving by McKenzie Wark, I found a resonance in how she repositions euphoria. Wark’s exploration of drug-induced empathy highlights how euphoria is not simply an indulgence but a transformative state, especially for those whose existence already lies at the periphery of capitalist norms. This aligns with what I call *phenobarbytal*—phenomenological rupture—a break from the usual way of experiencing reality. It’s not just about feeling good; it’s about being transported to an entirely different state of consciousness, one that resists societal control over emotions and refuse regulation. Euphoria is rarely a baseline condition; it is either chemically induced or arises from what psychiatry categorizes as mania. . Self-induced euphoria, whether through pharmaceuticals,

psychedelics, or party drugs, is deeply stigmatized, yet what it ultimately offers is not just escape but a radical leak—a pharmacological refusal to remain within sanctioned emotional architectures. If capitalism demands affective discipline, euphoria leaks and becomes an unruly excess, an ecstatic disordering of time, perception, and embodiment. Euphoria is incentivised within certain type of heteronormativity. However when the house cracks, leaks out, to the streets, avenues, euphoric excess secretes onto those architectures.

This leakage of euphoria—once a controlled domestic condition, now an unsanctioned public excretion—reveals the porous nature of euphoria, between interior and exterior systems, the home and the street, the prescribed and the illegal. If Valium in the 1960s was engineered to dissolve the anxieties of white middle-class domesticity, its eventual spillover into public spaces marked a crisis of containment, where euphoria, detached from its original spatial regulation, became a social liability a choreographed spinal injury²(figures 16,17)standing away from capitalist demands. The transition from household tranquilizers to street opioids like fentanyl follows this same trajectory: a chemical architecture designed for control inevitably mutates into something ungovernable when its distribution leaks beyond its intended subjects. What was once a neatly packaged pharmaceutical promise—compressed into a pastel-colored tablet, a soft domestic fix—became an amorphous, collective movement in the streets, a choreography of bended nodded out bodies no longer bound by the architecture of rational labor and docile consumption. This disobedient slowness disrupting the tempo of urban circulation. The slow bending of the spine of opioid users in public, the euphoric bodies slumped on sidewalks and tent cities, materialises this shift in euphoria’s spatial logic: a once-private, medicated and welcomed by capitalist system, now made hyper visible, and stigmatised.

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 15

² <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9575565/> Spine injury exhibits a complex association with opioid misuse that predominantly operates through treatment factors. Spine injury patients may represent a subpopulation requiring early intervention to prevent opioid misuse

This echoes Wark's assertion that raving is not merely hedonistic escape but what I would call radical leak, a way of stepping outside capitalist affective discipline.

(McKenzie2023,p19)Pharmaceutical euphoria, when achieved by breaking the approved use, functions similarly: it disrupts the smooth operations of labor and order, transforming bodies in ways that go beyond their economic usefulness. Drug induced euphoric state outside of suburban households stands as a threat to capitalistic value, and as a direct problem of urban architecture. If the home was once the proper site for medicated tranquillity, then the streets—open air drug markets, underground clubs, train stations—become the stage for its euphoric residue, where sub-population euphoria is not just pleasure but a suspension of identity, a refusal of the architectures that demand coherence.

2.3. Pharmacokinetics - Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion.

The pill is an interscalar object, simultaneously specific and systemic, biochemical, and sociological. It permeates bodies, landscapes and culture, shaping individual subjectivities while inscribing itself into cityscapes and social structures as both cultural artefact and chemical compound. As Paul B. Preciado suggests, the pill is not just a pharmacological intervention; it is a chemical panopticon, a mechanism of self-surveillance that regulates behaviour, sexual activity, mental health, and even bodily aesthetics. (Preciado, 2013, p. 205). It is consumed, absorbed, and metabolized, but its residues extend bodily secretion systems such as urine and sweat. It expands to pop culture, arts and media. This leakage—chemical, visual, and ideological—reveals the pill's role as an infrastructural force modifying individual and public spaces.

The aestheticization of pharmaceuticals goes through what I call pharmacokinetics. The glossy barbiturate ads from 1960 slowly started to disappear, as it was becoming impossible for pharma companies to hide the fact that many iconic Hollywood stars died of barbiturate and other sedative overdoses. Movies like Valley of the Dolls portrayed barbiturates as both relief and ruination, just as 1980 "I Am Dancing as Fast as I Can" show how one prescription can turn you into an addict. Decades later, the rise of Yung Lean and Sad Boys aesthetics absorbed opioids and benzodiazepines distributed into digital aesthetics. Xanax bars became cultural symbols of self-medication and escapism. Pills entered the media without pharma companies moving a finger because the

Figure 11

Figure 13

prescriptions were in people's pockets. More recently, benzodiazepines like lorazepam have been critiqued in contemporary media, as White Lotus further embedding them into cultural narratives.

Walking in Rotterdam, I noticed graffiti tags reading "XANAX" appear in unexpected places: the

Figure 14

Figure 12

side of a residential building car park, and a new construction site in Rotterdam.(*Figures 11-14*)These inscriptions are urban excretions of pharmaceutical culture, making private consumption public. Like a pill dissolving into the bloodstream, these traces infiltrate urban space, shaping how cities register dependency, self-regulation, and control. The graffiti functions as both acknowledgement and rupture—it makes visible what pharmaceuticals are designed to suppress—chemical and pharmacological dependence. It is a leak in the system, an unintended marker of pharmaceutical presence. The secretion of branded names around urban structures reminds me of Hogshire "the most important thing about the pill is not its color or shape, and certainly not the formula itself, Is its name" (*Hogshire,1999, p38*). Looking at the graffiti, I think about the branded language etched into the built environment and check the names on my own prescriptions: *Lexotamil, Lexapro*. A quick search reveals that *lex* in Latin means *law*. These little pills imagined as laws but inscribed not on constitution but on their chemical background.- my body and its interiors are a site of governance

As Emma Cheatle proposes in her theory of part architecture, the domestic- medical space is not total or fixed but fragmentary, leaky, and temporally unstable. This resonates with the pharmacological infrastructures I trace here—pills and their residues create spatial traces that are partial, uncontained, and culturally metabolized. Like the Translucent glass facade in *Maison de Verre*, XANAX graffiti seduces and invites but does not open doors. "XANAX" tags are not complete structures but fragments: part-architecture, part-leak. These leaks are unconfined pharmacological influence and its cultural materialisation, externalising it into public statements. The pill is metabolised and eliminated in a form of this leak.

Architecture, too, metabolizes. It absorbs and secretes, modulating visibility, access, and control. Suppose the graffiti marks an uncontrolled seepage of pharmaceutical influence into public space. In that case, Maison de Verre offers an architectural counterpoint—an experiment in controlled transparency, where glass does not reveal but filters, veils, and disciplines perception. A house between intimate and medical operates like a biopolitical mechanism: regulating flows, administering exposure, and structuring the body's relationship to space. Just as the pill functions as treatment and containment, Maison de Verre embodies a paradox—an enclosed, transparent, porous and clean yet saturated with medical gore a clinic with a bedroom.

To understand how architecture, like pharmaceuticals, mediates bodies and behaviours, we must turn to containment of leaks and their eventual structural collapse.

3.Transition : Centrifuge Tubes

Hospital corridors are constantly bleached, and the blood, piss, shit, placentas and bodily fluids are in constant motion. As I sit in the hospital corridor with my number 435, I smell it all. But all memories of those smells are wrapped because of this little hint of lemon-flavoured bleach.I enter the doctor's cabinet, and I start to leak from my eyes. Uncontrollably. Into the soft fabric of my sleeves, into my lap, into the sterile silence. This leaking is not noted. It is absorbed. I was prescribed 140 pills of SSRi, 30 benzodiazepines, and 45 beta blockers. And given instruction. Months later now and I realised, that was the last time I cried. I realised, the flood doesn't begin with the leak. It begins with the container pretending it's dry.

3.1.Container: A Typology of Containment and Collapse

Trigger warning : sexual violence

Figure 18

I sat in the chair across from my doctor. My tears are pulled silently into the medical infrastructure. They join the secretions of others—sweat, blood, and amniotic fluid. My Grandfathers self-inflicted hospitalised suicide. My parent's future remains in soaking formaldehyde. All collected. All were eventually discarded. I am not alone in leaking, in fact, everything leaks. That's what the bleach is for: to erase the memory of secretion. To make sure the container looks clean for the next patient.

This sterility of the hospital environment, designed explicitly for control and order, systematically erases the most intimate human aspects of care—connection, presence, and dignity. This tension resembles Michel Foucault's "medical gaze," a diagnostic process emphasizing the subtle perception and modulation of symptoms. Prior to the late 18th century, medicine prioritized vitality, flexibility, and fluidity. The shift to modern frameworks brought a new emphasis on categorizing deviations from a standardized model of health (*Foucault, 1973, p. 35*). Foucault argues that clinical experience is not timeless or universal but historically constructed through changing perceptions of the body and mind. This chapter presents Maison De Verre as architectural apparatus of tension between containment, sterility and leakage.

In Preciado's analysis of Foucault in *2012 Architecture As A Practise Of Biopolitical Disobedience*, the one of the main takeaways about the architecture of clinics is a suggestion to move from ananamorphic model of interpreting spatial relationships to a biopolitical model, where architecture is understood as a political artifact. Foucault identifies "tertiary spatialization" as the dynamic interface where medical practices confront societal forces—political struggles, economic constraints, and social utopias—reshaping perceptions of health and space. The Maison de Verre, then, emerges not just as a site of care or modernist aesthetic, but as an active participant in the systemic containment and erasure of bodily leakage. Its transparent surfaces mask a biopolitical regime, polished and wiped clean with bleach. It is within this layered interaction that medicine finds the origins of its most radical transformations and redefinitions (*Foucault, 1973*).

Figure 19

Figure 20

The Maison de Verre is a house built to contain the illusion of transparency. Built between 1928 and 1932 for gynaecologist Dr Jean Dalsace and his wife, the house is made of translucent glass bricks that diffuse light without revealing form. It appears to offer openness, modernity, and the freedom of air and hygiene. But what it performs is a choreography of control. Every glass tile is a pharmaceutical promise: you will be seen but not exposed. *You will be examined but not held. You will be cured, but only if you don't spill.* For the sake of this thesis, I look at this house as an architectural apparatus of containment.

Emma Cheadle describes this as part-architecture: an aesthetic of partial visibility, part-leak, in fact part-screen. The patient becomes a silhouette, never a person. Preciado shows us how architecture, like pharmacology, does not simply house bodies but transforms them. The Maison de Verre becomes a machine for biopolitical modulation, a clinical dream, a wet fantasy that refuses to get dirty.

Inside this house, the female body goes through an aestheticized and routinized medical spectacle. The tiles shine with diffused light, first from the exterior already to the gynaecological tools that are only partially. The surfaces resist absorption. The body is meant to pass through, to comply, to disappear back into the facade. "the light turned into her. At this moment, the building performs the clinical act—dividing the self into flesh and symptom. "caught hanging vertically between the two floors, cut in two by the horizontal line of the floor slab," the resident and the patient cut mirrored and refracted. (Cheatle 2017, p98).

The Maison de Verre shines its modernist aesthetics and almost surgical detail floor plan developed by Pierre Chareau and other architects, yet Emma Cheadle exposes the building's ambiguous and porous reality. She notes how its supposedly sterile surfaces and transparent logic obscures the Madame Dalsace and doctor Delsace marriage, she appears as the owner of the house, and silhouette of a patient in different forms and locations. "it indicates erotics between gynaecological practise and her own marriage. (Cheatle, 2017 p. 103). The house does not simply separate the clinic from the home—it blurs them. This intentional ambiguity echoes pharmacological leakage through translucent glass, partial thresholds, rooms that half-reveal and half-conceal. In this space, world of medicine oozes from its designated zone and invades the personal. The architectural boundaries designed to contain the clinical are perforated, aestheticized. Leakage becomes the other spatial logic, perhaps not intended by the architects.

In this thesis I treat architecture as biopolitical device, it is worthy to mention following Emma Cheatles thoughts X ray architecture by Colomina. “ she notes, modern architecture is system of a surface designed to protect expose and discipline the body. (Colomina, 2019)These surfaces do not merely reflect light; they reflect ideology—an obsession with hygiene, control, and visibility. The promise of order becomes a camouflage for deeper ruptures, which we are not allowed to see. The house, the clinic, and my medicine cabinet all leak. It is how containment becomes intimacy, and how control becomes embodied.

Figure 21

Figure 22

When Emma Cheatles wrote about this space, she connected this house with Large Glass (figure 22) by Marcel Duchamp, through their shared themes of fragmentation, transparency, visibility, and concealment of desire and voyeurism. I think of my family's medicine cabinet. Opaque, seductive, domestic. Concealing the pills and family photos. But all of these objects are cracked: Duchamp's *Large Glass*, the *Maison de Verre*, and the medicine cabinet in my house—they act as floodgates—constellation of architectures that pretend to contain but cannot. Each performs a version of desire: aesthetic, medical, domestic. And each leaks. I bring them together not to force a comparison, but to show how all spaces of care and control fracture under pressure, revealing their hidden fluids. They disguise their secretions as calm lakes, but eventually, they collapse. And I am brought to the moment when I was too high on benzodiazepines from that medicine cabinet to say no to a guy fucking me in the open street. My body floated, but I remember my neighbour passing by with dogs. I remember stillness. I remember not saying yes. I remember not saying anything. And then I remember nothing. It brings back Duchamp's *Large Glass* with cracked desire. *Maison De Verre* together with cracked glass bricks holes of sexual display. Housewives who end up in open air drug markets sleeping on the pavement.

The crack and a leak is not a failure- it is exit. The leaks finally are visible and uncontained. Here, I want to highlight again the architecture typology of leaking, sweating, and wetness. This is not a objective but method of rethinking architectural control. While architecture is unquestionably a container, it also acts as floodgates: political, medical, and psychological. And then the separation between architecture and the flesh starts to disappear—architecture no longer surrounds the body; it leaks from it.

3.2.The end - Floodgate

Leaking—whether through fluids, memory, or resistance—exposes the fragile fictions of containment, revealing that bodies, spaces, and histories are always porous.

There is no such thing as a perfectly sealed architecture. Not in hospitals. Not in homes. Not in neurotransmitters or pills. The floodgates always give way.

Floodgates are not just metaphors. They are physical thresholds that fail. IV bags overflow. Pipes burst. Docile housewife break. Placental blood hits the floor. Pharmaceutical waste seeps into rivers, sediments, fish. Neurotransmitters resist the instructions they're given. You cry when you shouldn't. You sweat in the examination room. Your body remembers things the clinic would rather it forget.

I want to think of architecture as a floodgate. Not as a wall. Not as a skin. But as a pressure point that holds until it doesn't. To design with wetness in mind is not to control it, but to choreograph its failure. The pill leaks into the bloodstream. The pill name leaks into graffiti.

Like the pill, the city absorbs us until it doesn't. Then it leaks. Homelessness. Nodding bodies. Tent cities. The choreography of the spine slowly collapsing into the sidewalk. This is euphoric architecture, chemical architecture, failed containment. It is not architecture as safety, but as saturation. The Maison De Verre tried to contain. It failed. Not because it broke, but it was absorbed by wider biopolitical system, But we need to emphasise that architectural ideas are political and cultural artefacts like pills they infiltrate buildings built to hold the body and to outlast the fluids it tries to filter. But no tile is strong enough. No clinic is sterile enough. No home is safe enough.

And I think that's where we begin again. Not in the clean cabinet. Not in the glass tile. But in the leak. The residue. The refusal to dry up.

Let the architecture leak.

Let the secretions gather.

Let the design fail, and in doing so,

flood us

with new shapes,

systems,

typologies and archetypes.

Glossary

Biopolitics: Coined by Michel Foucault, it refers to the way institutions (medicine, law, education) regulate human bodies and populations through systems of control. In this text, architecture becomes a biopolitical apparatus, shaping not just behaviour but even molecular life.

Biopower: The mechanisms of power that operate on bodies and populations, shaping behaviour, identity, and life through surveillance, discipline, and normalization.

Wetness: A metaphor and core element of this work, for the permeability and fluidity of systems, spaces, and bodies, highlighting how architecture is dynamic. Representing both control subversion. Wetness blurs boundaries between dichotomies like inside/outside, control/resistance, self/system. It suggests that these categories are not fixed but fluid, allowing for interaction and transformation.

Aspects ;

Permeation/ Penetration - permeation refers to the way external systems, substances, or structures physically interact with the human body by crossing its boundaries.

Leak - resistance in a form of uncontrolled secretions. Leaks also happen inside structures, metaphorically and physically presenting actions against constraints. A method for rethinking architectural typology, where individuals can navigate and choreograph leaks and failures and sometimes subvert the systems that permeate their lives.

Secretions - Bodily outputs such as tears, sweat, semen, saliva, and pharmaceutical waste that blur boundaries between internal and external, personal and systemic. In this thesis, secretions are both metaphor and material—Secretions mark points where the self meets system, and where control fails.

Architectures of discipline - refers to physical, social, and institutional structures designed to control, regulate, and normalize human bodies and behaviours. Drawing on Foucault's concept of biopolitics, these architectures include spaces like hospitals, clinics, schools, and even domestic environments, such as the **medicine cabinet**, which act as tools of surveillance and enforcement of societal norms.

Phenobarbital - A neologism mixing *Phenobarbital* (a sedative drug) and phenomenology. Used to describe a rupture in lived experience—a pharmaceutical break from normative perception, often achieved through euphoria or altered states. It's not just about feeling good; it's about being transported to an entirely different state of consciousness, one that resists societal control over emotions.

Pharmakokinetics (reimagined) - Usually describes how drugs are absorbed, metabolized, and excreted. In this thesis the term is expanded to describe how pills travel through culture, architecture, and emotion, leaking into graffiti, ads, memory, and design..

Ambient control - In this thesis, ambient control helps explain how systems of governance are no longer merely institutional, but molecular and emotional—infusing domestic, public, and digital spaces with imperatives for stability, calm, productivity, and compliance.

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Figure 22 Marcel Duchamp The Bride Stripped Bare by Her Bachelors, Even (The Large Glass)

The End .